

Researcher Engagement with Data Management

About this template

This project aims to collect case studies from different organisations around the globe on how to engage with the research community about research data management. By asking various questions about the models used and also about the organisational context, we hope to create a useful resource for organisations which are looking to increase their engagement with their research communities.

Who should fill this in?

Anyone who would like to share their case study. Don't worry about someone else from your organisation contributing the same story - we will review, consolidate and de-duplicate all the content received and we will attribute all the contributors.

How to fill this in?

Please think about methods of researcher engagement you use which you think might be of interest to other organisations. If you would like to mention several ways of engaging researchers, please fill in the template below for every method separately.

Please indicate as many activities as you like by repeating the template below for every method separately. If you do not want to list them all, indicate the one(s) you think might be of greater interest to other organisations.

If you don't know the answers to some of the questions, skip them.

What will happen with the data?

We will edit and publish case studies under CC BY licence on the RDA website and as a textbook (we reserve the right not to publish all the case studies submitted). We will attribute all the published contributors and indicate your affiliations, unless you indicate that you prefer your name/your organisational affiliation not to be indicated. All contributions will be reviewed and edited before publishing and the authors will be contacted before the case studies are published to approve the content. If no contact information is provided, the members of this RDA project will do the editing.

By answering the questions below you agree for the data processing as described above.
For any questions, please contact the project coordinator Marta Teperek: m.tepererek@tudelft.nl

gdpr - Consent to collect personal data in the survey.

This survey is collecting personal data: names, surnames, email address, and position. We collect your contact information in order to provide you with proper attribution for your contribution and also to contact you to approve revised case studies before publication. The demographic data collected in this survey is for statistical purposes and your identity will not be disclosed. As we will collect above listed personal information, we kindly ask you to agree to the collection of your personal information before completing the survey. Details about collecting, storing and processing your information in this survey can be found [here](#). of Privacy policy and general terms are available on this [link](#).

Please indicate whether you agree with collecting your personal information. You can still fill in the survey even if you do not agree with collecting your personal information:

- No, I do not agree with collecting my personal information
- Yes, I agree with collecting my personal information

Q1 - About your institution**Q2 - How many researchers (excluding PhD students) work at your institution?**

- 100 or less
- 101 - 250
- 251 - 500
- 501 - 1,500
- 1,501 - 5,000
- 5,001 - 10,000
- 10,001 or more

Q3 - How many PhD students are studying at your institution?

- 100 or less
- 101 - 250
- 251 - 500
- 501 - 1,500
- 1,501 - 5,000
- 5,001 - 10,000
- 10,001 or more

Q4 - What are the main research disciplines at your institution?

Multiple answers are possible

- Social Sciences
- Arts & Humanities
- Biological Sciences
- Medical / Clinical Sciences
- Physical Sciences
- Applied Sciences
- Engineering Sciences
- Other:

Q5 - How many employees (FTE) carry out RDM-support activities as part of a centralized service or a service to multiple departments across your institution

- Less than 1
- 1 - 3
- 3 - 5
- 5 - 10
- More than 10

Q6 - How do you engage with your research community about data management?

Q7 - Activity title

Q8 - Activity Objective

Q9 - Activity Description

Q10 - Link to a website/resource about the activity

Q11 - Target Audience

Multiple answers are possible

- First Stage Researchers (up to the point of PhD)
- Recognized Researchers (PhD holders or equivalent who are not yet fully independent)
- Established Researchers (researchers who have developed a level of independence)
- Leading Researchers (researchers leading their research area or field)

Q12 - Characterise the main drivers for this activity

Multiple answers are possible

- Top-down
- Bottom-up
- Disciplinary
- Centrally-coordinated
- Researcher-led
- Other:

Q13 - How costly is this activity?

	Inexpensive	Low cost	Fair	Costly	Very costly
Cost of materials:	<input type="radio"/>				
Infrastructure:	<input type="radio"/>				
People's time:	<input type="radio"/>				

Q14 - What are the resources required to run this activity? Think about materials, infrastructure, but also human resources.

Q15 - What mechanisms do you use to assess whether these activities drive cultural change at your institution?

Q16 - In your opinion, what is the overall value for money of this activity? (costs in terms of direct financial costs, personnel, infrastructure, etc. vs ability to drive cultural change)

	Poor	Questionable	Fair	Acceptable	Excellent
Value for money:	<input type="radio"/>				

Q17 - Challenges associated with this activity

Q18 - Opportunities associated with this activity

Q19 - What do you think could be improved about this activity?

Q20 - Would this activity be easy to implement at another institution? (think about both costs and cultural aspects)

	Very easy	Easy	Moderate	Difficult	Very difficult
Cost:	<input type="radio"/>				
People aspects:	<input type="radio"/>				

Q21 - Why the implementation is easy/difficult? (Regarding to the previous question)

IF (1) gdpr = [2]

Q22 - About you

IF (1) gdpr = [2]

Q23 - Your name(s) and surname(s)

IF (1) gdpr = [2]

Q24 - Your email address(s)

IF (1) gdpr = [2]

Q25 - Your institution

IF (1) gdpr = [2]

Q26 - Are you happy for us to list you as the author(s) of this case study and also indicate your organisational affiliation?

- Yes, publish my name and organisational affiliation
- Only publish my name
- Only publish my organisational affiliation
- Don't publish my name, or the organisational affiliation

IF (1) gdpr = [2]

Q27 - Your position

- Librarian
- Data manager
- Data scientist
- Researcher
- Project manager
- Data archivist
- Computing staff

Other:

C1 - Computation